

Evaluating Forensic Log Readiness in Simulated 6G Networks

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Abstract—The forensic readiness of future 6G networks will depend not only on advanced detection systems but also on maintaining the integrity, availability, and timeliness of the system and event logs. In high-speed, ultra-low-latency environments, the risk of delayed or compromised logs is an issue for incident response and post-incident forensic analysis. This paper evaluates local and remote log collection mechanisms in a simulated 6G network environment. Benign (low intensity) and adversarial (high intensity) traffic was generated to measure log collection performance in a Cisco router and a centralised Linux server. The results show that while log completeness is maintained in both cases, recording local logs on the router can exhibit delays up to 50s (peak delay) under high-intensity traffic, whereas remote logs are unaffected. These findings highlight the trade-off between speed and forensic reliability in high-throughput environments and show the importance of log adaptability to improve forensic readiness in the face of next-generation communication systems.

Index Terms—6G Networks, Log Forensics, Network Forensics, Forensic Readiness, Network Simulator, GNS3

I. INTRODUCTION

Logs are critical forensic artefacts, used for real-time intrusion detection and post-incident timeline reconstruction. However, the transition to 6G networks, where ultra-low latency, distributed architectures, and edge nodes can complicate forensic reconstruction, magnifies the shortcomings of conventional log recording techniques. As data flows become increasingly transient and decentralised, the ability to capture logs that are both rich in forensically critical content and resistant to tampering without introducing overhead becomes a core challenge for next-generation networks. Devices such as routers and edge gateways might have limited storage or CPU capability, resulting in the loss or delay of forensic data in periods of high traffic [1]. This raises the question whether forensic readiness in 6G networks should prioritise local logging for immediacy or remote logging for resilience.

Network forensic readiness aims to enhance the collection of credible digital evidence while reducing incident response costs.

A. Local Versus Remote Logs

Local logging writes logs to the device or network node where events occur (for example, server logs are written to the local disk). Remote logging sends data over the network, perhaps to a localised log centre. In a 6G context, local logging may reduce network overhead; however, it can risk loss of evidence if the device is compromised or has limited storage (which is very possible for storage to fill up in high-traffic environments). On the other hand, a remote approach might be more secure if local nodes are compromised, but at the same time, it introduces latency and adds more traffic to the network.

There is limited work on how logs behave under realistic load conditions in terms of delay before visibility, and how remote versus local logs affect that delay. This paper addresses this gap through simulation-based experiments in GNS3, comparing local and remote log collection in a simulated 6G high-speed network. The contributions of this paper can be summarised as follows:

- A simulated 6G network using the GNS3 network simulator in a practical and reproducible manner to evaluate the forensic performance of local and remote log collection.
- Measurement and comparison of log delay and completeness under varying traffic intensities.
- An evaluation that highlights that real-time visibility may require trade-offs with system resilience, specifically in the context of local log availability despite complete log retention.

The remainder of the paper is organised as follows: Section II offers a brief literature review of related work on forensic readiness in 6G networks. Section III presents the experimental methodology and simulation setup. Section IV

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provides detailed results of the log delay analysis. Finally, a discussion of the results and possible avenues for future work is outlined in Section VI.

II. RELATED WORK

A. Forensic Challenges in 6G Networks

According to [2], a key challenge of log forensics in 6G networks is the aggregation of data across edge servers, due to the volume of data, different formats, encryption, and the need for real-time monitoring. Data is also moving through the network, as edge devices might not be able to handle computational demands and offload computational tasks to the cloud [3]. This poses a challenge for investigators who must “hunt” for data across multiple cloud servers and perhaps jurisdictions, correlate it, and create effective timelines while maintaining data accuracy and integrity [2].

The large volume of data generated and to be logged also raises the question of what *must* be logged. As [4] points out, most open-source applications produce logs that are structurally inefficient for digital forensic investigations. In a 6G network, the correlation of local and remote logs across multiple edge devices becomes an even greater challenge. Determining log data requirements is not a new topic [5], but it is one where the community still lacks consensus. Standards such as NIST SP 800-92 [6], emphasise log management but remain vague on log content. Recently, [7] highlighted how missing causal links in logs can impair cross-host analysis, an issue that is likely to be more pronounced in 6G networks. This underscores the importance of achieving a balance between the immediacy of local logs and the scalability and availability of remote logs.

B. 6G Forensic Readiness

Early efforts introduced specialised frameworks to proactively prepare for investigations. For example, [8] proposed a dedicated IoT forensic readiness model that outlines how connected devices can continuously log and safeguard evidence for future incidents. Similarly, [9] developed a smart readiness model for shadow IoT devices, unauthorised or unseen devices in a network, focusing on automated event monitoring and tamper-resistant logs even for those hard-to-detect endpoints. These frameworks highlight the need for advanced mechanisms beyond traditional enterprise logging, given the scale and heterogeneity of 6G ecosystems. A common theme is the incorporation of emerging technologies to ensure the integrity and availability of evidence. Blockchain in particular has been considered as a backbone for forensic data provenance: its decentralised, append-only ledger can guarantee that evidence tampering is evident across different administrative domains. For example, [10] investigated the use of blockchain to secure inter-drone communication in 6G networks by creating immutable audit trails of drone telemetry and interactions. Such a blockchain-envisioned UAV framework can inherently support forensic readiness by design, ensuring that any data collected by aerial nodes is chronologically chained and verifiable. Similarly, [11] proposed an AI-powered drone network for

critical 6G applications (such as telesurgery) that not only uses blockchain for trust, but also uses machine learning to detect anomalies in real-time, triggering forensic data capture when network conditions or drone behaviour deviate suspiciously. These works illustrate a trend towards holistic forensic readiness frameworks that blend blockchain trust guarantees, AI adaptive analysis, and even UAV integration as roaming data collectors, a combination that aims to address the forensic challenges of the massive and ubiquitous connectivity of 6G.

C. Real-Time Evidence Collection

Achieving low-latency, real-time evidence collection is another focal point in recent 6G forensics-related research. With 6G expected to support applications demanding millisecond-level responsiveness, forensic readiness approaches are evolving to capture volatile data before it vanishes. One promising approach is Federated Learning (FL) for distributed attack detection. Instead of funnelling all data to a central server, FL enables edge devices (e.g. smart cameras, IoT sensors, base stations) to collaboratively train detection models on-site, sharing only intermediate parameters. This design not only protects privacy but also dramatically cuts down the time to insight. The framework proposed by [12], combined FL with blockchain to create a decentralised forensic system for IoT, where edge nodes locally analyse data for signs of intrusion and then record evidence metadata on-chain for integrity and consensus. The study emphasises strategically capturing the state of the system in snapshots to preserve ephemeral evidence. Rather than continuously logging everything, [13] proposed a proactive safety scheme that monitors and predicts the onset of a stealthy attack and automatically triggers targeted data collection at that moment. This on-demand forensic logging ensures that crucial evidence (e.g. sensor readings or actuator commands right before an incident) is saved with minimal delay, without the prohibitive overhead of constant recording. Likewise, there is a push for edge-based logging in volatile environments: critical network functions are equipped with local storage and analysis capabilities so that data in transit (or in a transient state) is immediately duplicated at the nearest edge node. By keeping forensic logs at the network’s periphery, for instance, within a base station or IoT gateway, investigators can later retrieve relevant evidence even if the central systems were compromised or if the data existed only briefly in memory. Such designs have been shown to significantly reduce forensic data loss and collection time, as the evidence is gathered and filtered at the source in real-time, rather than shipped raw over possibly congested links.

D. Low-Latency Forensic Data Transmission

Recent work is investigating how to transmit and process forensic data with minimal latency by harnessing novel 6G architectures. One approach involves the use of reconfigurable intelligent surfaces (RIS) that can dynamically beamform or reflect signals to optimise communication. RIS technology can improve the throughput and reliability of wireless links, which is advantageous when large forensic data (e.g. raw

sensor logs or video evidence from an incident) needs to be collected quickly from the field. Alongside physical-layer innovations, architectural innovations such as open radio access network (Open RAN) are creating opportunities to embed forensic readiness into the network fabric itself. Open RAN disaggregates the base station into software-driven components with open interfaces, allowing operators to deploy custom analytics and security agents at the edge of the network. [14] proposed a digital forensics and incident response (DFIR) module for Open RAN implementations, in which a small agent is installed in the radio unit and distributed unit of a 6G base station. This agent can sniff local traffic for anomalies, buffer relevant packet traces, and even apply machine learning models to flag attacks in real-time, all before the data flows into the core network. Such a design enables immediate evidence collection. The malicious packet or exploit attempt is captured at the RAN node and can be frozen for analysis. The concept of localised processing for forensics extends to multi-access edge computing (MEC) nodes and even user devices, by processing data near its source. Only distilled alerts or summaries (far smaller in size) need to be transmitted back to the investigators, which significantly reduces latency. This aligns with the broader 6G trend of pushing intelligence to the edge; as noted by [15], intelligence at the edge nodes is becoming the “backbone” of future services, and this applies equally to forensic services.

E. Positioning This Work

While prior work has proposed architectural frameworks for achieving forensic readiness in 5G and emerging 6G networks, few studies have empirically evaluated the operational performance of their constituent mechanisms. This paper aims to address this gap by focusing specifically on the timeliness and completeness of log collection, a technique foundational to any forensic readiness strategy.

III. METHODOLOGY

The proposed system is designed to detect and monitor any changes in logging infrastructure on a router or local server during a cyber attack scenario within a simulated 6G network environment. The network architecture includes multiple components: workstations, a local server, a switch, a Cisco router, and its connectivity to a cloud-based platform, as illustrated in Figure 1. The objective is to observe the system’s behaviour under attack and to preserve relevant network and system logs for forensic analysis. Log delay was measured as the time difference between the appearance of the corresponding log entry on the local and remote systems. All clocks were synchronised before testing.

A. Simulation Tools

To implement the attack scenario and ensure comprehensive logging, the proposed system employs three primary tools. First, *Graphical Network Simulator 3 (GNS3)* is used to simulate the network architecture, enabling the creation of a realistic and controlled network environment. Second, a *Linux*

Fig. 1. Network Topology Used in the GNS3-based Simulation Environment.

server is incorporated to store system and network logs locally, ensuring the availability of data for post-incident analysis. Third, *Wireshark* is utilised for the continuous monitoring and recording of network traffic and validating the logs generated by the router, facilitating detailed forensic investigation and aiding in the detection of anomalous or malicious activity during the simulated cyber attack.

1) *Graphical Network Simulator 3 (GNS3)*: GNS3 is an open-source graphical network emulator in Python, designed to replicate complex network environments. It enables the emulation of real network operating systems by using various underlying emulators as discussed in [16]:

- **Dynamips**: A Cisco IOS emulator(Cisco 7200 ISO version), used to simulate Cisco routers by running actual IOS images. It serves as a virtualisation hypervisor, allowing the operation of multiple router instances with full IOS command-line functionality.
- **VirtualBox**: A general-purpose hypervisor used to run server and desktop operating systems, including support for Juniper JunOS.
- **QEMU**: A powerful open-source machine emulator capable of running Cisco ASA, PIX, and IPS devices.

GNS3 is a highly effective platform for simulating real-world networking scenarios, particularly for testing security mechanisms and forensic logging under attack conditions.

2) *Linux Server*: The Linux server is used to store system and network logs locally to serve as a central repository for forensic analysis. *Rsyslog* [17] was configured to receive and archive logs generated by the router within the simulated network environment. This configuration ensured secure and centralised log storage. The purpose of collecting and storing logs on the Linux server was driven by a key constraint observed in 6G environments of limited on-device storage capacity, particularly in routers. In such high-speed, resource-constrained environments, local router logs tend to be short-

term and are often overwritten or lost due to insufficient storage. Redirecting logs to the Linux server in real time ensured that critical forensic data, including system alerts, traffic patterns, and routing events, could be preserved beyond the volatile memory constraints of the router. This approach improves the reliability and completeness of forensic evidence collection in next-generation networks.

3) *Attack Machine*: A Linux machine is used to simulate different attack scenarios within the virtual network environment. This machine is configured to generate various types of malicious traffic, including reconnaissance, denial of service (DoS), floods, and spoofing attacks aimed at the Cisco router. This component is critical to creating a controlled and realistic adversarial environment to validate the attack detection and log preservation mechanisms. This approach enabled repeatable simulations of both high and low intensity attack vectors to ensure a comprehensive evaluation of the logging mechanism and network forensic readiness of the proposed system under different attack scenarios.

4) *Wireshark*: Wireshark is an open-source network packet analyser tool. Wireshark is deployed to monitor and capture traffic within the simulated network environment. It is configured in promiscuous mode, which allows visibility of all the network packets passing through the network interface. It helps filter network packets and save a *pcap* file for further analysis and forensic investigation. The use of Wireshark is to ensure that all aspects of network packets, such as communication protocols, vulnerabilities, and attack patterns, can be recorded and used for forensic investigation. Wireshark is built-in and integrated into the GNS3 emulator to monitor the network traffic of any device.

IV. EXPERIMENTS AND RESULTS

A simulation network utilised a Cisco 7200 router ISO image to evaluate the logging on the router and the local server. The network topology comprises a single router, five workstation nodes, a local server, and an attacker node. The router was assigned the IP address *192.168.1.1/24*, while the workstations, server, and attacker node were configured with the same subnet. To facilitate monitoring of potential attack traffic, system logging was enabled using the *logging console debugging* directive, with timestamping configured to improve event traceability. An inbound access control list (ACL) was applied on the router interface to log all IP traffic destined for the router, thereby capturing connection attempts and traffic patterns. ACL commands such as *access-list 101 deny ip any any log, interface FastEthernet0/0*, and *ip access-group 101 in*, have been used to log the denied traffic. ICMP-based reconnaissance and TCP connection anomalies were observed using the targeted debugging commands such as *debug ip icmp* and *debug ip tcp transactions*. This allows real-time network-level event monitoring and evaluation of the native capability in detecting and logging simulated attacks.

The local server is configured for centralised logging by activating *rsyslog*. It is configured to forward router-generated logs to a local server within the same LAN. This setup uses

two configuration files: *rsyslog.conf* for loading necessary modules and files within, and *rsyslog.d* to specify detailed logging rules. Two modules are loaded to enable syslog reception over both UDP and TCP protocols, as shown in Listing 1.

```
# provides UDP syslog reception
module(load="imudp")
input(type="imudp" port="514")

# provides TCP syslog reception
module(load="imtcp")
input(type="imtcp" port="514")
```

Listing 1. Rsyslog configuration to enable UDP and TCP syslog reception on port 514.

Following the configuration of both the router and the local server for logging, the attack machine executed various types of attacks using a *Python* script. These attacks included reconnaissance, denial of service (DoS), flooding, and spoofing, all directed toward the router. In contrast, traffic originating from the workstation remained benign, simulating normal network behaviour. Initially, the router successfully detected and recorded the attacks without a noticeable delay, as illustrated in Listing 2.

```
May 4 21:19:02 _gateway 56: *May 4 21:19:02: %
SEC-6-IPACCESSLOGDP: list 101 denied icmp
192.168.1.100 -> 192.168.1.1 (0/0), 1552
packets
May 4 21:21:02 _gateway 57: *May 4 21:21:02: %
SEC-6-IPACCESSLOGDP: list 101 denied udp
192.168.1.100(0) -> 192.168.1.1(0), 171
packets
May 4 21:21:13 _gateway 58: *May 4 21:21:13: %
SEC-6-IPACCESSLOGDP: list 101 denied tcp
192.168.1.100(0) -> 192.168.1.1(0), 1
packet
May 4 21:24:03 _gateway 59: *May 4 21:24:03: %
SEC-6-IPACCESSLOGDP: list 101 denied icmp
192.168.1.100 -> 192.168.1.1 (0/0), 640
packets
May 4 21:26:02 _gateway 60: *May 4 21:26:02: %
SEC-6-IPACCESSLOGDP: list 101 denied udp
192.168.1.100(0) -> 192.168.1.1(0), 137
packets
May 4 21:27:02 _gateway 61: *May 4 21:27:02: %
SEC-6-IPACCESSLOGDP: list 101 denied tcp
192.168.1.100(0) -> 192.168.1.1(0), 44026
packets
```

Listing 2. Network Traffic Logs During Low Intensity Traffic from Workstations to Router.

To evaluate the impact of traffic load on logging performance, five workstations were introduced to generate simultaneous network traffic toward the router, simulating 6G conditions. Under this high-traffic condition, the same set of attacks was executed again. A significant delay in log recording was observed on the router, indicating performance degradation under increased traffic load. However, the local server's logging system showed no such delay, as demonstrated in Listing 3.

```

*May 5 14:27:45: %SEC-6-IPACCESSLOGDP: list
101 denied icmp 192.168.1.10 ->
192.168.1.1 (0/0), 350 packets
*May 5 14:27:45: %SEC-6-IPACCESSLOGDP: list
101 denied icmp 192.168.1.20 ->
192.168.1.1 (0/0), 339 packets
*May 5 14:27:45: %SEC-6-IPACCESSLOGDP: list
101 denied icmp 192.168.1.30 ->
192.168.1.1 (0/0), 332 packets
*May 5 14:27:45: %SEC-6-IPACCESSLOGDP: list
101 denied icmp 192.168.1.40 ->
192.168.1.1 (0/0), 324 packets
*May 5 14:27:45: %SEC-6-IPACCESSLOGDP: list
101 denied icmp 192.168.1.50 ->
192.168.1.1 (0/0), 316 packets
*May 5 14:27:45: %SEC-6-IPACCESSLOGDP: list 101
denied udp 192.168.1.100(0) ->
192.168.1.1(0), 142 packets

```

Listing 3. Network Traffic Logs During High Intensity Traffic from Workstations to Router.

To further examine the logging performance of the local server under stress, heavy traffic was redirected specifically towards the server. Even under this load, no logging delays were observed, which confirms the stability and reliability of the centralised logging system, as presented in Listing 4.

```

May 5 14:44:38 _gateway 23: *May 5 14:44:39: %
SEC-6-IPACCESSLOGDP: list 101 denied icmp
192.168.1.100 -> 192.168.1.1 (0/0), 1
packet
May 5 14:47:54 _gateway 24: *May 5 14:47:55: %
SEC-6-IPACCESSLOGDP: list 101 denied udp
192.168.1.100(0) -> 192.168.1.1(0), 174
packets
May 5 14:49:54 _gateway 25: *May 5 14:49:55: %
SEC-6-IPACCESSLOGDP: list 101 denied icmp
192.168.1.100 -> 192.168.1.1 (0/0), 1227
packets
May 5 14:53:54 _gateway 26: *May 5 14:53:55: %
SEC-6-IPACCESSLOGDP: list 101 denied udp
192.168.1.100(0) -> 192.168.1.1(0), 196
packets
May 5 14:54:54 _gateway 27: *May 5 14:54:55: %
SEC-6-IPACCESSLOGDP: list 101 denied icmp
192.168.1.100 -> 192.168.1.1 (0/0), 1081
packets

```

Listing 4. Network Traffic Logs During High Intensity Traffic from Workstations to Local Server.

Table I summarises the results of the above-mentioned test scenarios. While no packet loss or log corruption was observed, local logging exhibited delays of up to 5 seconds under sustained traffic, whereas remote logging remained stable and timely.

TABLE I
LOGGING DELAY AND COMPLETENESS ACROSS LOAD CONDITIONS

Scenario	Attack	Log Location	Delay	Complete
Normal Load	DoS, Floods, and Spoofing	Router	✗	Yes
Normal Load		Server	✗	Yes
High Load		Router	✓	Yes
High Load		Server	✗	Yes
Targeted Server Flood		Server	✗	Yes

These findings show that forensic logging in 6G networks cannot rely solely on local logs, even if log completeness is preserved. In sustained traffic, the router spends more time processing logs than forwarding packets and queues log messages internally. The delay in log availability can impede timely response in time-sensitive investigations.

V. DISCUSSION

The findings of this study highlight that local logging under network load introduces significant delays in log visibility. Although no log entries are lost, the delay affects both real-time threat detection and post-incident forensic correlation. This is likely attributed to resource contention, where routers prioritise packet forwarding over log processing during high-traffic scenarios, such as DoS attacks. Furthermore, the integrity of log timestamps is compromised. Since logs are written only when the router becomes available, the recorded timestamps may differ slightly from the actual event times. This can result in inaccurate timeline reconstruction and potentially misleading information during forensic investigations. The preservation of logs helps forensic investigators to reconstruct the event. Nevertheless, the preservation of logs, even when delayed, is a key component of forensic readiness, as it enables investigators to reconstruct events. Ensuring that logs are correctly retained and timestamped supports both forensic readiness and investigative accuracy.

This work offers valuable insight into the behaviour of logging mechanisms on routers and local servers within a simulated 6G network environment, both under load and under normal operating conditions. However, there are several limitations that should be acknowledged.

A. Limitations

- The current evaluation has not been performed on physical network devices or with real-world traffic, which may exhibit different performance characteristics.
- The study does not examine the impact of cloud-based logging or evaluate the delays introduced by network connectivity when transmitting logs to remote servers.
- Alternative simulation platforms, such as EVE-NG and mininet [18], have not been explored for comparative evaluation.

B. Future Work

Future research should focus on evaluating the differences in logging behaviour between local and cloud-based systems. In particular, assessing the impact of logging on system resource utilisation, including CPU usage, memory consumption, and network bandwidth, would provide a further understanding of performance trade-offs. Furthermore, experiments involving physical devices and real network traffic would enhance the applicability and relevance of the results. Something else to be considered is the impact of secure logging mechanisms, including log encryption, anonymisation, and privacy-preserving computation techniques such as secure multiparty computation. These approaches are likely to play a significant

role in 6G contexts, where data sensitivity, user privacy, and distributed edge architectures demand careful balancing of forensic utility with compliance and trust. While remote logging demonstrated superior timeliness and completeness under load, it also introduces specific security concerns.

VI. CONCLUSION

This study assessed log readiness in 6G networks by comparing local and remote logging under simulated high-intensity traffic. Local router logs exhibited delays of up to 50 s during sustained attacks, risking timestamp inaccuracies and delayed threat detection. Remote logging to a centralised server maintained stability, highlighting its reliability for forensic integrity in resource-constrained 6G environments. While simulations confirmed log completeness, real-world validation and cloud-based logging remain unexplored. Future work must prioritise physical device testing, cloud integration, and resource efficiency analysis to align forensic frameworks with 6G's ultra-low latency demands. These findings underscore the need for adaptive logging strategies to ensure timely, accurate investigations in next-generation networks.

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